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Research Article

**STUDY OF BLOOD GLUCOSE LEVEL AT DIFFERENT BODY
MASS INDEX AMONG PATIENTS VISITING OPD**¹Dr. Muhammad Ishfaq, ²Dr. Mehwish Sagheer Khan, ³Dr Nazia Ali¹House Officer Bahawal Victoria Hospital Bahawalpur²Nishtar Hospital Multan³THQ Kotli Sattian**Abstract:**

Objective: To study the relation between serum glucose and BMI in patients visiting opd belonging to different lifestyles.

Material and methods: This cross sectional study was conducted at Department of Medicine Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur from July 2017 to December 2017. Total 166 patients either male or female having age from 18 years to 24 years were selected. Serum blood glucose was measured and BMI was calculated.

Results: Minimum age of patients was 17 years and maximum age was 23 years. Mean age of the patients was 19.17 ± 1.5 years, mean BMI was 24.65 ± 6.196 and mean serum glucose level was 126.23 ± 25.56 mg/dl. The Pearson correlation test showed that the level of level of serum glucose increased with increasing BMI. This positive correlation was statistically significant ($r = 0.625$, $P = 0.000$).

Conclusion: Findings of current study showed a positive correlation between BMI and serum glucose levels. Significant different between mean serum glucose levels and different age groups was detected. Results of this study also showed that there is insignificant difference between serum glucose levels of male and female patients.

Keywords: BMI, correlation, serum glucose, obesity, BVH, Outdoor department

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INTRODUCTION:

In general population, adiposity is measured by body mass index (BMI). BMI is calculated as weight in kg, divided by square of height in meters.¹ An individual can be divided into different categories according to their BMI i.e. under weight (if BMI ≤ 18.5), normal weight (if BMI ranges from 18.5–24.9), over weight (if BMI ranges from 25 to 29.9) and obese (if BMI is ≥ 30).² Increased BMI can be a risk for carcinomas, stroke and heart diseases.³ In patients of type-II diabetics, obesity is a modifiable risk factor. The mechanism by which obesity induces insulin resistance is poorly understood. Several biological products (free fatty acids, leptin, adiponectin, TNF- α and resistin) secreted by adipocytes, which modulated the insulin secretions. Weight of body and insulin action may be responsible for insulin resistance.⁴ It is assumed that there is a positive correlation between serum sugar levels and BMI. Obesity is one of the major public health problems globally. In different parts of the world the average BMI is rising few percent/decade, thus fuelling the concern about the effects of increased adiposity on health.⁵ So, a study was planned to detect the correlation between BMI and serum glucose among the patients.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross sectional study was conducted at Department of Medicine Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur from July 2017 to December 2017. Total 166 patients either male or female having age from 18 years to 24 years were selected. Patients with any

systemic disease were excluded from the study. History was taken from all the patients regarding family history of diabetes mellitus. Weight and height of all the patients was measured by weighing machine and measuring tape to calculate BMI. Random blood sample was drawn and sent to laboratory for serum glucose levels. Findings of the laboratory test and BMI were entered on pre-designed proforma along with demographic profile of all the patients. All the collected data was entered in SPSS version 21. Mean and SD were calculated for age, BMI, serum glucose level. Frequencies were calculated for gender and family history of DM. Pearson correlation test was applied to check the correlation between BMI and serum glucose levels. Stratification was done for age, gender and family history of DM. Post stratification student t test was applied to detect the difference of serum glucose levels for these variables. P value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

Total 166 patients were selected for this study. Minimum age of patients was 18 years and maximum age was 24 years. Mean age of the patients was 19.17 ± 1.5 years, mean BMI was 24.65 ± 6.196 and mean serum glucose level was 126.23 ± 25.56 mg/dl. The Pearson correlation test showed that the level of level of serum glucose increased with increasing BMI. This positive correlation was statistically significant ($r = 0.625$, $P = 0.000$). (Table 1)

Table 1: Correlation of BMI with serum glucose

	Serum glucose (mg/dl)	
	Pearson correlation (r)	P-value
BMI	0.254	0.009

Patients were divided into two age groups i.e. age group 18-20 years and 21-24 years. Total 160 patients belonged to age group 18-20 years and only 6 patients belonged to age group 21-24 years. In age group 18-20 years, mean serum glucose was 126.96 ± 25.68 mg/dl. In age group 21-24 years, mean serum glucose level was 106.33 ± 9.24 mg/dl. Statistically significant ($P = 0.025$) difference of mean serum glucose between both age groups was noted. (Table 2)

Table 2: Comparison of mean serum glucose level between the both age groups

AGE GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	P VALUE
18-20 YR	160	126.96	25.68	0.025
21-24 YR	06	106.33	9.24	

Male patients were 77 and female patients were 89. Mean serum glucose level of male patients was 128.64 ± 26.24 and mean serum glucose level of female patients was 124.15 ± 24.92 . The difference of mean serum glucose levels between male and female patients was statistically insignificant with p value 0.714. (Table 3)

Table 3: Comparison of mean serum glucose level for gender

GENDERN	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	P-VALUE
MALE	77	128.64	26.24	0.714
FEMALE	89	124.15	24.92	

Total 91 patients found with family history of DM and 75 patients found without family history of DM. Mean serum glucose level was 124.23 ± 25.50 mg/dl in patients with family history of DM and 128.65 ± 25.59 mg/dl without family history of DM. The difference between mean serum glucose level between both groups was statistically insignificant with p value 0.813. (Table 4)

Table 4: Comparison of mean serum glucose level for gender

Family hx of DM	N	Mean	Standard deviation	P-value
Yes	91	124.23	25.50	0.813
No	75	128.65	25.59	

DISCUSSION:

In current study a positive correlation ($r = 0.254$) between serum glucose and BMI was detected. In different studies of the world, positive correlation was also detected between serum glucose and BMI.^{6,7} Ethnicity also affects the association between diabetes mellitus and obesity which may explain the various levels of association between the serum glucose levels and obesity reported by different studies.⁸ In age group 18-20 years, mean serum glucose was 126.96 ± 25.68 mg/dl. In age group 21-24 years, mean serum glucose level was 106.33 ± 9.24 mg/dl. Statistically significant ($P = 0.025$) difference of mean serum glucose between both age groups was noted. Increasing incidence of obesity globally is attributed to dietary habits and changing in life styles.⁹ The mechanism by which obesity induces insulin resistance is poorly understood. Obesity causes peripheral resistance to insulin-mediated glucose uptake and may also decrease the sensitivity of the beta-cells to glucose.¹⁰ These changes are largely reversed by weight loss, leading to a fall in blood glucose concentrations towards normal levels. Weight gain precedes the onset of diabetes; conversely, weight loss is associated with a decreased risk of type 2 diabetes.^{11,12} The administration of resistin, an adipocyte derived hormone, decreases while the neutralization of resistin increases insulin-mediated glucose uptake by the adipocytes. Thus, resistin may be a hormone that links obesity to diabetes.⁴ Leptin is produced by adipocytes and is secreted in proportion to the adipocyte mass. It signals the hypothalamus about the quantity of stored fat. Studies in humans and animals have shown that leptin is associated with obesity and insulin resistance.¹³ The deficiency of adiponectin, an adipocyte-derived hormone, plays a role in the

development of insulin resistance and subsequently, type 2 diabetes.¹⁴ Retinol-binding protein 4, free fatty acids, tumour necrosis factor-alpha, plasminogen activator inhibitor 1, interleukin-1 beta, uncoupling protein 2 and obestatin are also implicated in the adipose tissue induced pathogenesis of type 2 diabetes.¹⁵ BMI is a good measure of adiposity; however, the relationship between actual body fat and BMI differs between ethnic groups, and as a consequence, the cut off points for the overweight status and obesity based on BMI, will have to be ethnicity specific.¹⁶

CONCLUSION:

Findings of current study showed a positive correlation between BMI and serum glucose levels. Significant difference between mean serum glucose levels of different age groups was detected. Results of this study also showed that there is insignificant difference between male and female patients.

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